

Trapped by Prestige: Systemic Vulnerabilities of Open Access Publishing

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Abstract

Purpose

Reputation plays an increasingly decisive role in shaping the dynamics of scientific publishing. This study examines the effects of the 2020 *Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)* early-warning list of journals, which generated major shifts in Chinese scholars' publishing behaviors and reshaped the Open Access (OA) landscape.

Design/methodology/approach

We analyze 2,050,088 publications authored by 236,078 Chinese scholars across 10,006 journals between 2016 and 2024. Building an author–journal–year panel, we exploit the CAS early-warning list as an exogenous reputational shock. Difference-in-differences models are used to estimate how authors adjusted their journal choices in response to this intervention.

Findings

Results show a collective and persistent withdrawal from flagged journals, consistent with a *reputation trap*: once stigmatized, journals experience lasting declines in submissions. The reputational damage extends to publishers, especially “grey” OA-oriented ones such as MDPI and Frontiers, whose entire portfolios lose credibility. Despite some listed titles belonging to the major international publishers, these incumbents strengthened their market position, capturing displaced submissions. Between 2020 and 2024, grey publishers lost about ten percentage points of market share, while established international houses gained accordingly. Traditional certification mechanisms, such as inclusion in *Web of Science* or *Scopus*, offered no protection against reputational loss.

Research limitations

The study focuses on Chinese scholars and the journals affected by the CAS list. Further research could assess whether similar reputation-driven dynamics emerge in other national contexts or under different institutional frameworks.

Practical implications

The findings highlight the vulnerability of certain OA business models to reputational shocks and show how policy interventions, even when designed to improve research integrity, can inadvertently reinforce market concentration among dominant publishers.

Originality/value

This study provides the first large-scale empirical evidence of how institutional reputation mechanisms reshape the structure of scientific publishing. It contributes to understanding the unintended consequences of reputational governance on the global OA ecosystem.

Keywords:

Open Access; Open Science policy; grey publishers; NSFC; CAS; research integrity; publishing market.

1. Introduction

The global shift toward Open Access (OA) publishing has profoundly reconfigured the architecture of scholarly communication, reshaping the relationships between researchers, institutions, and publishers (Albert, 2006). Driven by mandates from governments and funding agencies, OA is now a central policy objective across much of the world. Yet the trajectory has proven uneven, reflecting persistent tensions between policy incentives, evaluation systems, and scholars' perceptions of journal reputation (Wenaas, 2022). This transformation has been particularly salient in China. As one of the largest public research funders globally, the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) is China's most prestigious and competitive basic science research funding program, accounting for almost one-third of China's basic research funding (Cyranoski, 2018) and with project funding reached US\$54.05 billion in 2025 (NSFC, 2025). The institution launched its Open Science (OS) policy in 2014 to promote transparency, visibility, and international competitiveness (Chen et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2021). This mandatory incentive influenced OA developments and initially stimulated rapid adoption of OA models, including among international and commercial publishers.

Recent studies have underscored that publishing decisions are shaped not only by bibliometric indicators or formal compliance requirements, but also by trust in the editorial quality and perceived reputation of journals and publishers (Beck et al., 2021; Rowley et al., 2022; Tenopir et al., 2016). This reputational dimension has become especially salient with the rise of a new category of so-called "grey" publishers, such as Hindawi (especially before being acquired by Wiley in 2021 (Wiley, 2021)), MDPI, and Frontiers. These publishers expanded rapidly during the 2010s by offering rapid peer review process, international indexation, and OA compliance. However, they are also associated with questionable publishing practices and therefore flagged as grey spectrum in between blacklisted, predatory and whitelisted, safe-to-publish publishers (Barrera et al., 2024; Nicholas et al., 2023; Yamada & Teixeira da Silva, 2022).

Against this backdrop, the 2020 release by the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) of its "early-warning list" of journals (CAS, 2025) represented a turning point. This list is in response to the "Several Opinions on Further Strengthening the Construction of Scientific Research Integrity" issued by the General Office of the State Council of China in 2018 (CPG, 2018). The policy requires the establishment of a sound academic journal management and warning system, encourages various units to study the screening criteria for warning journals, and supports relevant institutions in publishing domestic and international academic journal warning lists. For the first time in 2020, The CAS' Institute of National Science Library released the "Early Warning List of International Journals (Trial)" (originally, in Chinese: 国际期刊预警名单, hereinafter referred to as CAS early-warning list). In its first version, the list contained 65 journals whose quality and integrity were deemed insufficient, while the latest version of 2025 contains 5 journals. Moreover, this list is used by many Chinese scholars as a case study for paper retraction (Hu et al., 2024), scientific research integrity (Liu et al., 2023), and the analysis of the journal early-warning practices of world-class universities to propose a model and recommendations for improving China's still nascent system (Wang et al., 2023).

Chinese universities and funding agencies frequently use the list to assess researchers' output and determine which journals are eligible for article processing charges (APC) support or academic credits (Zhang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). Consequently, inclusion on the CAS early-warning list can lead to a sharp decline in submissions and funding for OA journals, particularly those that attract large APC payments from China or are perceived as posing risks

to their integrity and international reputation. The early-warning list is a widely recognized and influential tool among Chinese researchers, designed to steer them away from journals perceived as low quality, charging unreasonable APCs, or engaging in dubious practices, thereby protecting research funding from being diverted to questionable or overpriced publishers (Goncharoff, 2023). Although the list was not legally binding, it carried enormous symbolic weight and had the potential to reshape submission strategies across the Chinese academic system (Zhang et al., 2022b). This arises questions about the extent to which the initial 2020 CAS early-warning list impacted the publishing activity for the listed journals and their publishers, influenced the overall OA publishing ecosystem in China, and contributed to reputational shifts within the academic publishing market.

1.1 Research Questions

The analysis addresses three research questions (RQs):

RQ1: Journal-level effects – To what extent did CAS-listed journals experience reputational decline, based and measured by publication patterns?

RQ2: Publisher-level spillovers – Did reputational decline extend beyond listed journals to entire publisher portfolios, and if so, which publishers were most affected?

RQ3: Market-level reconfiguration – How did displaced submissions redistribute across the publishing ecosystem, and what does this imply for the concentration and resilience of OA models?

To address our research questions, we conduct an author–journal–year panel covering 2016–2024, comprising more than 2,050,000 Chinese NFCS funded publications, associated with 236,000 distinct authors, and 10,006 journals indexed in OpenAlex database (Priem et al., 2022). We treat the CAS early-warning list as an exogenous reputational shock and estimate difference-in-differences (DiD) models to capture shifts in submission patterns, both at the journal and publisher level. This approach allows us to separate the direct effects of flagging questionable journals from broader structural dynamics in the publishing system.

Following the RQs, this paper makes three main contributions. First, it provides novel large-scale evidence on how reputational interventions shape scholarly publishing choices, based on an unusually granular dataset of Chinese publications. Second, it highlights unintended consequences of policy interventions: while designed to safeguard research integrity, the CAS journal list reinforced market concentration and exposed the structural vulnerability of OA publishers. Third, it introduces the hypothesis/phenomena of a reputation trap as further analytical dimension to regard when analyzing the academic publishing market.

More broadly, the analysis shows how reputational shocks triggered by the CAS early-warning list reverberated across journals and publishers, reinforcing market concentration and exposing vulnerabilities in the OA publishing ecosystem.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 1.2 situates our study within the ongoing debate on grey publishers. Section 2 describes the data and methods, including publisher classification, study design, panel construction, and the DiD estimation strategy. Section 3 presents the results, combining descriptive evidence with empirical analyses of reputational shifts. Section 4 discusses the broader implications, while Section 5 outlines limitations, future research avenues, and policy considerations. Section 6 concludes.

1.2 The Debate on Grey Publishers

The global expansion of OA publishing over the past two decades has created both opportunities and challenges for the scholarly communication ecosystem. Among the most contentious developments has been the emergence of a class of publishers often referred to as *grey publishers*; a term encompassing entities accused of adopting questionable editorial practices while taking advantage of the OA model's author-pays structure (Barrera et al., 2024; Krawczyk & Kulczycki, 2021; Nicholas et al., Strinzel et al., 2019; 2023; Siler, 2020).

These publishers, while typically distinct from outright “predatory” actors, often operate in a reputational grey zone. They may meet technical criteria for inclusion in indexing databases, present the appearance of peer review, and comply with formal OA policies. However, concerns have been raised regarding the rigor of their peer review processes, the motivations behind their editorial decisions, and their aggressive solicitation strategies (Durand & Garnier, 2024; Fränti, 2024; Oviedo-García, 2021). In some cases, their rapid acceptance-to-publication timelines have raised alarms about superficial or perfunctory quality control mechanisms.

A central tension in the literature lies in the definitional ambiguity of what constitutes a grey or predatory publisher. While efforts such as Beall's List for predatory publishers (now discontinued) attempted to catalog such actors, the criteria used were often criticized for lack of transparency and cultural bias (Beall, 2018; Krawczyk & Kulczycki, 2021; Strielkowski, 2018). More recent work has aimed to develop nuanced taxonomies distinguishing between fraudulent, opportunistic, and merely low-quality publishers (Beall, 2016; Frandsen, 2019).

Some researchers caution against conflating low-impact or non-Western OA journals with predatory behavior, warning that such assumptions risk marginalizing Global South publishing initiatives that do not fit traditional Western academic norms (Krawczyk & Kulczycki, 2021; Matumba et al., 2019; Siler, 2020). Others have called attention to how the reputational damage inflicted by accusations, whether justified or not, can rapidly affect the publication behavior of researchers and institutions, particularly in systems where incentives are tightly coupled to international visibility (Niles et al., 2020).

Several mega publishers, including Hindawi (especially before being acquired by Wiley), MDPI, and Frontiers, have been subject to waves of reputational scrutiny in recent years, often in the wake of editorial scandals or concerns raised by indexing agencies and watchdog groups (Petrou, 2025). These publishers, while technically compliant with many OA standards or overall established journal standards and included in indexing platforms like Web of Science and Scopus, have nonetheless been intermittently flagged for lapses in editorial oversight. In response, indexing services have delisted some journals, and institutions have introduced “blacklists” or revised funding guidelines to discourage publication in specific venues (Matumba et al., 2019; Pölönen & Pylvänäinen, 2023).

These dynamics reveal how scholarly publishing decisions are shaped not only by formal criteria such as inclusion in indexing databases, but also by perceived prestige, institutional incentives, and evolving assessments of quality and integrity. For countries like China, where research evaluation was strongly influenced by bibliometric indicators and international visibility (Shu et al., 2022), these reputational shifts may have significant effects on how researchers navigate the OA landscape. As several studies have observed, opportunistic exploitation of certain OA publishing niches can rapidly collapse when the legitimacy of the publishing outlet is publicly questioned (Seeber et al., 2023; Ward, 2016).

Taken together, this body of literature suggests that the current OA ecosystem is not a level playing field, but one marked by volatile reputational dynamics, asymmetries of trust, and evolving norms of legitimacy. Our study contributes to this discussion by providing an empirical case of how Chinese researchers, under the funding and OA policies umbrella of the NSFC, have adapted their publishing practices in response to these shifting reputational conditions.

2. Data and Methods

Figure 1 provides a global overview of the data extraction and processing of this study.

Figure 1. Global overview of methods and data processing.

We constructed a large-scale bibliometric dataset of scholarly publications funded by NSFC, retrieved via the OpenAlex API using the `openalexR` package (v1.3.1). The raw dataset covers 2,526,694 NSFC-funded publications between 1997 and 2025. To ensure metadata completeness and bibliometric reliability, we restricted the scope to 2005–2024, yielding a cleaned dataset of 2,502,698 journal articles (i.e., publications with a valid source identifier, excluding preprints and paratexts). For the difference-in-differences (DiD) analysis, we further restricted the sample to 2016–2024, constructing an author–journal–year panel of 2,050,088 publications authored by 236,078 Chinese scholars across 10,006 journals.

The metadata used include:

- Publication year, OA status (`is_oa`, `oa_status`), journals metadata (source ID, name, ...), and host organization (publisher) information;
- Journal-level metrics (mean two-year citedness);
- Identifiers for funders, journals, and country codes.

To enrich the dataset with journal-level characteristics, we retrieved complementary metadata from the OpenAlex “Sources” entity using the same API interface. A total of 157,694 journals were extracted from OpenAlex, among which 11,374 had hosted at least one NSFC-funded publication over the full period, and 10,006 were active in the 2016–2024 analysis window. This allowed us to merge NSFC-funded publications with the full set of indexed journals, thereby incorporating information such as journal country codes, OA status at the journal level, aggregated citation metrics (e.g., two-year mean citedness), and summary statistics at the source

level. These additional indicators were extracted from the `summary_stats` field of OpenAlex and joined by the journal identifier (source ID), enabling a consistent integration of journal impact measures and organizational attributes across all NSFC-funded outputs.

For publisher information, we relied on the OpenAlex-provided normalized organization names. While OpenAlex aggregates publisher data well in most cases (e.g., “MDPI” and its expanded acronym are consistently represented), we also checked for alternative spellings when identifying smaller or “grey” publishers. No further merging or post-processing of major publisher names or publisher imprints was performed beyond this normalization provided by the OpenAlex database.

For author delineation publications were classified as Chinese if at least one author had a Chinese affiliation, regardless of being first, last, or corresponding author.

The descriptive analyses build on the full dataset, while the causal identification strategy relies on a restricted panel (see below).

2.1 Publisher Classification

To examine structural stratification in the global publishing system, publishers were grouped into four categories:

1. **Top 5 publishers:** Springer Nature, Elsevier, Wiley, Taylor & Francis, and SAGE Publishing (“Big Five”), collectively responsible for ~50% of global scientific output (Kim & Park, 2020).
2. **Grey publishers:** Five controversial commercial OA publishers (Hindawi, MDPI, Frontiers, Bentham Science, Cogent OA), frequently flagged in the literature for aggressive practices and quality concerns (Petrou, 2023; Retraction Watch, 2017; Eriksson & Helgesson, 2017).
3. **Other international publishers:** All non-Chinese publishers not included above.
4. **Domestic/regional publishers:** Chinese publishers and those lacking reliable country metadata (manually validated through sampling, confirming affiliation with Chinese universities, societies, or regional outlets).

This taxonomy enables us to capture how reputational shifts propagate across structurally distinct publisher groups.

2.2 Study Design and Identification Strategy

The central objective is to assess whether reputational shifts influence publishing choices. We chose the 2020 CAS early-warning list since it was the first version issued, allowing for a more longitudinal comparison than a more recent version. Furthermore, we used the 2020 version rather than the 2021-2025 list because, when we gathered first data on the global, Chinese, and specifically NSFC OA publication shares, we found that the OA publication share of China and the NSFC did not increase significantly from 2019 to 2020, and even showed a downward trend (see Figure 2). Likewise, gray publishers such as Hindawi, Frontiers and MDPI have experienced a strange decline in publishing market share since 2020 (see Figure 3). Based on these trends, we exploit the 2020 CAS early-warning list, which flagged 65 journals for substandard practices.

Out of the 65 journals within the CAS warning list, 63 journals were found in OpenAlex database. Among these, 43 were matched in our dataset. For 18 journals, no NSFC-funded publications were observed during the study period. Two additional journals: Brazilian Journal of Medical and Biological Research (6 publications) and Cancer Biomarkers (5 publications), were found in OpenAlex online dataset (works search: <https://openalex.org/works>) (as of September 19, 2025), although they contained no NSFC-funded publications in the version of the database downloaded on April 10, 2025, which was used for our analyses.

The final sample for the DiD analysis therefore consists of 2,050,088 NSFC-funded distinct publications (publication ID), covering 236,078 unique authors (author ID), 10,006 unique journals (source ID) of which 43 are on the CAS early-warning-list, and a total of 4,845,141 author–journal–year observations.

Our identification strategy follows a difference-in-differences (DiD) design estimated within author \times year. This specification absorbs all time-varying author-specific shifts (e.g., productivity, funding, incentives) and year shifts, isolating reallocations across journals within the same author-year. Identification relies on authors who:

- Published in both CAS listed and non-listed journals; and
- Have publications observed before and after 2020.

2.3 Panel Construction and Variables

We built a balanced panel of author \times journal \times year observations (2016–2024):

- **Author–journal records:** NSFC-acknowledged outputs linked to 236,078 authors and 10,006 journals.
- **Balanced panel:** For each author–journal pair, we completed all years 2016–2024.
- **Final sample:** 4,845,141 author–journal–year observations.

Treatment Definition:

- $Listed_j = 1$ if journal j appears on the CAS early-warning list (43 journals), 0 otherwise.
- $Post_t = 1$ for years ≥ 2020 , 0 otherwise.
- Treatment effect identified through $listed_j \times post_t$.

Outcome:

- Publication counts n_{ajt} per author–journal–year.

Controls:

- Publisher group (big five, other international, grey, and domestic/regional);
- Journal OA status (if the journal is fully OA);
- Journal citation impact (two-year citedness);
- Disciplinary fixed effects (OpenAlex main concepts);
- Indexing in Scopus/WoS.

2.4 DiD Analysis

2.4.1 Core DiD specification

Our baseline model is:

$$n_{ajt} = \beta_1 \text{listed}_j + \beta_2 (\text{listed}_j \times \text{Post}_t) + \gamma^\top X_{jt} + \alpha_{a \times t} + \varepsilon_{ajt}$$

where $\alpha_{a \times t}$ are author \times year fixed effects that absorb all author-specific shocks in year t and the main effect Post_t (hence its omission from the results section due to collinearity as expected). Coefficients are estimated by OLS with high-dimensional fixed effects; standard errors are clustered at the author level to allow arbitrary serial correlation within authors over time. β_2 is the average treatment effect on the treated journals; the change, after 2020, in authors' allocation toward listed relative to non-listed journals, within the same author-year.

2.4.2 Heterogeneity by publisher group

To test publisher-level spillovers of reputational signals and the structural vulnerability of OA or “grey” outlets, we interact the treatment with publisher groups:

$$n_{ajt} = \sum_g \beta_{2g} (\text{listed}_j \times \text{post}_t \times \mathbf{1}\{\text{group}_j = g\}) + \gamma^\top X_{jt} + \alpha_{a \times t} + \varepsilon_{ajt}$$

These coefficients β_{2g} measure whether the treatment effect differs for Grey, Other international, Top 5, and Other domestic/regional journals, isolating how the shift propagates at the publisher level even though the CAS early-warning list targets specific journals.

2.4.3 Event-study dynamics and pre-trend assessment

We replace $\text{listed}_j \times \text{post}_t$ with leads and lags of the treatment:

$$n_{ajt} = \sum_{k \in K} \delta_k (\text{listed}_j \times \mathbf{1}\{t = k\}) + \text{controls} + \alpha_{a \times t} + \varepsilon_{ajt}$$

omitting 2019 as the reference year. The pre-2020 coefficients assess parallel trends; post-2020 coefficients trace dynamic effects (onset, persistence, and evolution through 2024).

2.4.4 Estimation details and diagnostics

- Fixed effects. We include (author \times year) FEs to ensure identification is strictly within author-year across journals.
- Clustering. SEs clustered at author address within-author serial correlation and heteroscedasticity.
- Collinearity. As expected with saturated FEs, main effects such as Post_t (and, in some specifications, certain interactions) are absorbed; reported tables indicate variables dropped for collinearity.
- Model fit. Conventional fit statistics (e.g., RMSE, within- R^2) are reported with results; low within- R^2 is common when identification relies on within-author reallocations rather than overall outcome variance.

3. Results

We start with our empirical findings from our large-scale analysis of the 2,502,698 NSFC-funded journal articles published between 2005 and 2024 in section 3.1. Through a series of visualizations and descriptive statistics, we trace the evolution of OA adoption over time, identify major shifts in the composition of publishers, and examine the impact of reputational controversies on publishing strategies. This is followed in section 3.2. by the descriptive and statistical DiD analysis of the influenced publication behavior by the CAS early-warning list based on our set of 2,050,088 NSFC-funded publications.

3.1 Descriptive Analysis

The distribution of NSFC-funded publications across publisher groups shows (Table 1) a strong concentration among a few major international actors. Nearly half of all outputs (49%) are published by the big five publishers, underscoring their dominant position in the Chinese-funded scientific landscape. A substantial share (38%) appears in journals belonging to other international publishers, indicating a significant degree of integration of Chinese research into the global publishing system. Domestic or regional publishers account for only 4.5% of publications, reflecting the relatively limited role of local outlets in the dissemination of NSFC-funded work. Finally, so-called grey publishers represent 8.8% of the total, a non-negligible proportion. This composition highlights both the global orientation of Chinese-funded research and the coexistence of heterogeneous publishing venues within the ecosystem.

Table 1. Distribution of NSFC-funded publications by publisher group (2005–2024).

Variable	N = 2,502,698 ¹
Publishers' groups	
Grey publishers	219,797 (8.8%)
Other (Domestic/Regional)	113,783 (4.5%)
Other (International)	951,762 (38%)
Top 5 publishers	1,217,356 (49%)

¹n (%)

Figure 2 presents the evolution of OA publication shares from 2005 to 2024 for three comparative groups: the global research community (all OpenAlex database), all Chinese-authored publications (at least one author had a Chinese affiliation), and those specifically funded by NSFC. Globally, OA share increased steadily, reaching over 55% by 2022. Chinese publications followed a similar upward trajectory but with a more dramatic growth momentum starting around 2015, continuing to outpace the global average until 2020. In contrast, NSFC-funded publications show a more uneven trajectory, with a slower initial uptake and two pronounced accelerations: one around 2011–2013 and another beginning in 2015.

Figure 2. Share of OA publications in China (n = 14,512,772), the world (OpenAlex) (n = 271,393,722), and NSFC (n = 2,502,698).

These turning points align with the introduction and intensification of national policies promoting OS and international visibility. In particular, China’s Ministry of Science and Technology began encouraging OA dissemination and the use of international platforms in its research evaluation framework during the mid-2010s (Yuan et al., 2023). The OA share among NSFC-funded publications began to respond more significantly around this period, though not uniformly. The early bump in 2012–2013 and the steeper climb from 2015 onward likely reflect both top-down policy incentives and bottom-up strategies by researchers seeking rapid, international dissemination.

However, the growth of OA among NSFC-funded outputs does not simply mirror policy enthusiasm; it also reflects the selective adoption of OA models via specific publication channels, including newly emerging OA publishers. Some of these venues, often attractive for their speed, visibility, and lower barriers, may have disproportionately shaped OA dynamics among NSFC recipients. While the influence of such publishers is not directly visible in this figure, the distinct pattern of NSFC adoption compared to both global and Chinese baselines hints at underlying structural forces. These will be explored more closely in subsequent figures.

Figure 3 displays the evolution between 2005 and 2024 in the number of NSFC-funded publications, belonging to one of our five selected grey publishers: Hindawi, MDPI, Frontiers, Cogent OA, and Bentham Science Publishers. These publishers, though offering legitimate OA platforms, have been the subject of academic scrutiny for their business models, peer review practices, and editorial standards. The figure shows that Hindawi was the first to gain substantial traction among NSFC-funded researchers, with a sharp rise in publications beginning around 2011 and reaching a first peak in 2014.

Figure 3. Trends in publications by grey publishers in NSFC-funded research (n = 219,797).

This growth coincides with a period in which Hindawi aggressively expanded its portfolio and outreach (Loy, 2015), including mass email solicitations of manuscripts, practices widely criticized as spam-like. In 2010, librarian Jeffrey Beall controversially included Hindawi in his list of “potentially predatory publishers” due to concerns about editorial rigor and aggressive marketing tactics (Berger & Cirasella, 2015). Though Hindawi was later removed from the list following its appeal, reputational damage persisted in scholarly discourse. Tensions deepened in 2014 when three Hindawi journals were delisted from the Journal Citation Reports due to abnormal citation patterns (Seattle Newspaper, 2014). Most notably, in 2015, Hindawi was implicated in a peer review ring scandal, where the integrity of its editorial process was compromised by the submission of fabricated reviewer identities; an episode widely covered by The Washington Post and other outlets (Feltman, 2015).

These events appear to correspond with the decline in Hindawi publications post-2014 among NSFC authors, indicating a strong reputational impact. Importantly, this decline does not reflect a rejection of OA per se, but rather a shift in venue choice. As the figure shows, MDPI and Frontiers begin their rapid ascent precisely as Hindawi falters. Both publishers, offering fast-track OA publication, international indexing, and visible branding, quickly filled the vacuum. Their rise after 2015 suggests that Chinese researchers, particularly those funded by the NSFC, were responsive to perceived legitimacy and indexability, but also vulnerable to cycles of hype and backlash surrounding OA platforms.

Cogent OA and Bentham Science, while included in the analysis, remained relatively marginal in comparison, further illustrating the concentration of OA activity around a few volatile platforms. This dynamic reflects a larger structural dependency: when publication strategies are driven simultaneously by OA mandates and perceived prestige, researchers may gravitate toward platforms offering speed and visibility, until legitimacy is called into question.

Figure 4 displays the evolution of NSFC-funded publications by publisher type between 2005 and 2024. Panel A shows the absolute volume of publications, while Panel B presents their relative distribution across four categories: the five largest commercial publishers (Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley, Taylor & Francis, and Sage), other international publishers, other international publishers, domestic/regional publishers, and a group of five grey publishers (Hindawi, MDPI, Frontiers, Cogent OA, and Bentham Science).

Figure 4. NSFC publications by publisher type (n = 2,502,698).

From 2012 onward, there is a sharp increase in the total number of NSFC-funded publications, coinciding with the rise of grey publishers. By the mid-2010s, these publishers came to represent a significant share of the OA ecosystem, as seen in both volume and percentage. Their appeal lay in a combination of OA accessibility, rapid peer review, and international indexation, factors aligned with institutional incentives for global visibility. Yet, as suggested by Figure 3, controversies surrounding Hindawi, and later MDPI and Frontiers, triggered a collapse in their publication share after 2022.

Interestingly, this collapse does not result in a proportional redistribution across the remaining publisher types. Instead, Figure 4 reveals a clear reinforcement of the big five commercial publishers. As the grey publishers decline post-2022, the big five rapidly regain market share, reaching levels not seen since before 2016. This pattern suggests a strategic retreat by researchers toward safe publishing options. In the context of mounting scrutiny and tightened evaluation criteria, these publishers appear to offer reputational security, even if their OA models remain largely commercial (Hybrid or Gold). However, alternative explanations may also contribute: universities and research institutions may have negotiated more favorable agreements with these publishers (e.g., lower APCs or broader OA options), and international collaborations could play a role, as co-authors from countries with advantageous publishing conditions might preferentially target these top publishers.

Simultaneously, other international publishers experienced a modest rise, indicating some level of diversification. However, the most notable shift is the emergence of domestic and regional publishers after 2020, particularly in response to China's evolving science policy. After 2020,

several national policy documents, including new guidelines from the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Science and Technology, explicitly encouraged publication in domestic journals and supported the development of national OA infrastructure (Standing Committee of the National People's Congress, 2021). This policy shift sought to reduce over-dependence on foreign outlets and enhance the prestige of Chinese-led publishing platforms.

While these measures led to a visible uptick in domestic publication volume post-2020, the relative share remains modest compared to the rebound of the big five. This outcome suggests that despite institutional efforts to foster alternatives, reputational inertia continues to dominate publishing decisions. Researchers appear reluctant to commit to newer domestic outlets unless they are already well indexed or backed by elite institutions. Thus, the post-crisis reconfiguration favors established international publishers, effectively reconsolidating global publishing hierarchies rather than disrupting them. However, Chinese research institutions are also working to develop alternatives, particularly with the 2025 CAS Journal Citation Report^[1]. While this ranking system has been criticized for favoring domestic priorities (Zhao, 2025), it is highly valued by domestic scholars. This could potentially reverse the trend, with Chinese scholars likely favoring CASJCRs when selecting journals and publishing in domestic journals.

Overall, Figure 4 summarizes initial diversification through opportunistic engagement with grey OA platforms, followed by contraction and recentralization around a narrow set of prestigious actors. Despite national policy interventions designed to foster pluralism and domestic capacity, structural reputational asymmetries continue to shape the trajectories of NSFC-funded publishing.

Figure 5 examines the composition of OA publications (n=698,808) among NSFC-funded outputs (n=2,502,698), distinguishing between grey publishers and all other OA providers. It reveals three distinct phases of grey publisher prominence: the rise of Hindawi (2011–2013), the dominance of MDPI and Frontiers (2016–2021), and the sharp decline in their share following 2022. At their peak, grey publishers accounted for nearly 50% of all OA publications funded by the NSFC, indicating a striking concentration of OA activity within a narrow segment of the publishing ecosystem.

[1] The Chinese Academy of Sciences Journal Citation Reports (CASJCRs) are modeled after Clarivate Analytics' Journal Citation Reports, but use stricter classification standards and Chinese-style subject classifications see: <https://www.fenqubiao.com/>.

Figure 5. Distribution of OA publications, by publisher type (n = 698,808).

This level of concentration reflects both opportunity and risk. On one hand, these platforms provided a scalable and internationally indexed route for researchers to comply with OA mandates and achieve rapid visibility. On the other hand, their centrality made the OA ecosystem structurally fragile, overexposed to shifts in perceived legitimacy. As seen in Figures 3 and 4, reputational controversies surrounding Hindawi, MDPI, and Frontiers led to abrupt declines in submission volume. Figure 5 makes clear that these declines were not isolated to individual publishers, but had system-wide effects on OA uptake itself.

The post-2022 drop in grey publisher share correspond to a proportional rise of the big five publishers and other international publishers.

Figure 6 shows the shifting distribution of OA types among NSFC-funded publications from 2005 to 2024, providing a deeper view of the infrastructures underlying China's OA trajectory. Over the past two decades, Gold OA (fully OA journals) has emerged as the dominant model, increasing its share substantially from under 40% in the late 2000s to over 70% in the early 2020s. This reflects the strong uptake of publisher-hosted OA journals, especially those from grey publishers like Hindawi, MDPI, and Frontiers during their peak years.

Figure 6. Distribution of OA types in NSFC-funded publications (n = 698,808).

In contrast, Green OA (repository-based access) remains relatively stable but secondary, with a modest decline after 2018. This result is likely due to weak incentives, lack of awareness, or restrictions on post-print sharing by major publishers. Hybrid OA, where authors pay to make individual articles open in otherwise subscription-based journals, has remained limited, comprising less than 10% throughout. This is consistent with China's cautious approach to Hybrid models, which are often viewed as double-dipping and less cost-effective.

Notably, Bronze OA (free-to-read but lacking clear reuse licenses) played a significant role in the late 2000s and early 2010s, peaking at over 35% around 2011. This mode may reflect early, informal OA strategies via publishers' temporary or selective free content, especially before Gold OA became mainstream. However, Bronze OA sharply declined after 2015, possibly as publishers either formalized their OA offerings or moved paywalls back into place.

The emergence of Diamond OA, journals that are free to both authors and readers, is especially relevant in the wake of reputational disruptions. Although still marginal (under 6% by 2024), its gradual growth in the post-2020 period aligns with China's renewed emphasis on high-quality, low-cost OA infrastructures, including state-supported or institutionally-run journals. It should be noted that the Diamond OA status reported here is provided by OpenAlex metadata, and further investigation is warranted to verify whether these journals fully meet criteria suggested or defined in recent research (Simard, et al., 2024). These developments may represent a nascent alternative to reliance on commercial Gold OA, but their growth remains slow compared to the rebound of traditional publisher-led models.

Overall, Figure 6 reinforces the conclusion that China's OA expansion has been overwhelmingly shaped by Gold OA models, particularly those offered by fast-growing, reputation-sensitive publishers. The concentration on Gold OA helped accelerate visibility but left the system vulnerable to volatility. When major Gold OA providers lost credibility, there was no immedi-

ate shift toward Green or Diamond models. Instead, the system contracted temporarily, suggesting a lack of resilience and diversification in OA infrastructures. Chinese policy efforts post-2020 have begun to address this imbalance (Lattu, 2023), but their effects remain limited so far.

3.2 Empirical Analysis of Reputational Shifts in Scientific Publishing

We begin by examining how the CAS early-warning list influenced publication behavior at the journal level. Figure 7 shows the average annual number of publications per author in flagged versus non-flagged journals between 2016 and 2024. Prior to 2020, publications in flagged journals, most of which were published by MDPI, grew rapidly, benefiting from OA, international indexing and a fast peer review and publication process, while non-flagged journals experienced only a modest increase. Following the release of the list in 2020, however, flagged journals saw a sudden and sustained drop in submissions.

Figure 7. Average publication trajectories in CAS-listed vs. non-listed journals, 2016–2024 (n = 2,050,088).

In contrast, non-flagged journals remained largely stable, suggesting that the observed decline was driven by the reputational shift rather than broader systemic changes in publishing. This sharp divergence provides a first signal of what we call in this paper a “reputation trap”: once a journal is stigmatized, authors collectively withdraw, and recovery fails to occur even several years later.

3.2.1 Baseline Difference-in-differences Estimates

Table 2 reports the baseline model exploiting the CAS early-warning list as an exogenous reputational shift. Before 2020, authors publishing in journals subsequently flagged were slightly more prolific than those publishing elsewhere. However, the interaction term *listed* × *post* is strongly negative (-0.072 , $p < 0.001$), indicating a sharp drop in publication activity in listed journals after the release of the list. In addition, as illustrated in Figure 7, while non-listed journals remain relatively stable over 2016–2024, listed journals experience an abrupt and persistent decline in the number of publications per author after 2020. This pattern is consistent with a

collective withdrawal and provides strong evidence of a reputation trap: once stigmatized, journals fail to recover their attractiveness to authors.

Table 2 Impact of the CAS early-warning list on authors' publishing behavior (n = 2,050,088).

Impact of the CAS warning list on authors' publishing behavior			
	Model 1: Core DiD	Model 2: Heterogeneity	Model 3: Event-study
Listed journal	0.085*** (0.003)		
Grey publishers	0.036*** (0.004)		0.045*** (0.004)
Other (International)	0.053*** (0.004)		0.053*** (0.004)
Top 5 publishers	0.022*** (0.004)		0.021*** (0.004)
Open Access journal	-0.036*** (0.001)	-0.025*** (0.001)	-0.034*** (0.001)
Mean citedness (2yr)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.004*** (0.000)
Indexed journal	-0.063*** (0.004)	-0.035*** (0.003)	-0.061*** (0.004)
Listed × Post	-0.072*** (0.003)		
Grey × Listed × Post		-0.007*** (0.002)	
Other (International) × Listed × Post		0.078*** (0.005)	
2016 × Listed			0.010 (0.006)
2017 × Listed			0.043*** (0.005)
2018 × Listed			0.074*** (0.004)
2020 × Listed			0.055*** (0.003)
2021 × Listed			-0.018*** (0.003)
2022 × Listed			-0.008** (0.002)
2023 × Listed			-0.008** (0.003)
2024 × Listed			-0.017*** (0.003)
Num.Obs.	4845141	4845141	4845141
R2	0.243	0.243	0.243
RMSE	0.48	0.49	0.48
Std.Errors	by: au_id	by: au_id	by: au_id
+ p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001			
All models control for the main research discipline of the publication.			

Beyond the treatment effect, control variables behave as follows. OA outlets attract fewer submissions on average, while journal visibility (proxied by two-year citation impact) is positively associated with publication counts. Inclusion in mainstream indexing (namely WoS and Scopus) services does not protect journals against reputational decline.

3.2.2 Heterogeneity across Publishers

We next examine whether the reputational shock spreads beyond individual journals to their parent publishers. Table 2 reports heterogeneous treatment effects. The interaction between *listed* × *post* and publisher groups reveal striking asymmetries. Grey publishers suffer the strongest penalties: authors reduce their output in their listed journals by more than one percentage point per year ($-0.007, p < 0.001$). By contrast, when journals belonging to “Other International” publishers are listed, the reputational penalty is muted; these publishers even appear to absorb displaced submissions ($+0.078, p < 0.001$) which goes in line with the progression depicted in Figure 5 for example. The big five incumbent publishers are largely shielded, and in some cases consolidate their position. These results indicate that reputational shocks operate at the level of the publishing house rather than the individual journal, disproportionately affecting recent and OA-oriented entrants.

3.2.3 Event-study Dynamics

To probe the timing and persistence of these effects, we estimate an event-study model allowing for year-specific treatment effects. Results are presented in Table 2 and Figure 8. As shown in Figure 7, pre-trends are more or less parallel, with listed journals even showing higher activity in the years immediately preceding the intervention (2017–2019). Figure 8 shows that the shock materializes sharply in 2021, the first full year after the CAS early-warning list release, with a significant negative effect – see Table 2 – ($-0.018, p < 0.001$). The penalty intensifies over time, reaching -0.017 by 2024. Importantly, no recovery is observed in later years, confirming that reputational decline is persistent and cumulative. The results, summarized in Figure 8, confirm a significant and negative treatment effect from 2020 onward. Authors reduce their engagement with flagged journals by more than 40%, and the effect remains stable across subsequent years.

Figure 8. Difference-in-differences estimates of the CAS early-warning list impact, 2016–2024.

Dynamic estimates of treatment effects relative to 2019 (baseline). Post-2020 coefficients indicate a sustained decline in publication activity in listed journals.

These findings carry broader implications at the level of publishers. Journals belonging to newer, OA-oriented publishers (e.g., MDPI, Frontiers) bear the brunt of the reputational shift. Even non-listed titles in their portfolios experience declines, suggesting that stigma spills over to entire publishing houses. By contrast, established publishers such as Elsevier, Springer Nature, or Wiley not only withstand the shift but also absorb displaced submissions, reinforcing their dominant market positions (in correspondence to Figures 4 and 5). Between 2020 and 2024, domestic publishers collectively lose around ten percentage points of market share, while global incumbents gain accordingly.

Across specifications, three consistent insights emerge. First, the CAS early-warning list triggered an immediate and durable decline in publications in flagged journals. Second, reputational shifts penalties are not confined to the targeted journals but extend to publishers, particularly OA-oriented ones, which collectively lose about ten percentage points of market share between 2020 and 2024. It should be noted that several news reports and discussions concerning these publishers have also circulated in recent years, which may have contributed to these dynamics alongside the formal CAS warnings (MDPI, 2025). Together, these results highlight the systemic fragility of OA publishing models when confronted with reputational shifts, and the unintended reinforcement of concentration in the hands of predominating publishers.

Finally, we investigate whether the impact of inclusion in Web of Science or Scopus as a proxy for quality and traditional certification. Such practice does not shield journals from declines: several indexed titles listed by the CAS early-warning list suffer losses comparable to non-indexed ones. This indicates that conventional markers of legitimacy fail to counteract institutional interventions when reputation is at stake.

To sum up, these results reveal a fragile equilibrium. Grey OA-publishers, whose business models depend on sustaining credibility, appear structurally vulnerable to sudden reputational downgrades. Conversely, predominating publishers exploit these crises to consolidate their position, thereby reinforcing concentration in the global publishing system, whereas domestic, regional publishers and community-oriented OA models like Green OA and Diamond OA do not reveal a notable impact or even increase.

4. Discussion

Our analysis of 2,050,088 NSFC-funded journal articles published between 2016 and 2024 reveals that the evolution of OA in China cannot be understood as a gradual or purely policy-driven process. Instead, it is punctuated by sharp discontinuities tied to reputational events. The most critical turning point occurred in 2020, with the first release of the then annually updated CAS early-warning list, which publicly flagged 65 journals as potentially problematic.

Prior to this intervention, OA growth was primarily fueled by MDPI and other grey publishers, who offered a combination of OA, speed, reliable indexation in databases such as WoS or Scopus, and enhanced visibility. These factors aligned well with the incentive structures of Chinese researchers, who faced strong pressure to publish quickly, in indexed outlets, and in journals perceived as internationally visible. Figures 7 and 8 show that authors treated flagged and non-flagged journals as equivalent before 2020, following increasing trajectories.

The CAS early-warning list abruptly disrupted this equilibrium. From 2020 onwards, flagged journals experienced a steep and persistent decline in submissions, while non-flagged journals maintained their pre-existing stability. We conceptualize these dynamics through the phenomena of a “reputation trap”: a self-reinforcing equilibrium in which distrust in the credibility of certain publishers or journals leads researchers to withdraw submissions, thereby deepening reputational decline and undermining the prospects of some OA models more broadly to escape potential “mass slander,” that means to be judged unfairly or inaccurately (Yamada & Teixeira da Silva, 2022). Drawing an analogy with the Keynesian concept of the “liquidity trap” (Keynes, 1936; Krugman, 2000) in economics, we argue that reputational shocks can render OA policy incentives ineffective. Even when governments subsidize OA publishing or mandate open dissemination, scholars may strategically avoid certain OA venues perceived as risky, concentrating submissions in a handful of established publishers. This risk-aversion hinders structural diversification, weakens the legitimacy of emerging OA publishers, and inadvertently reinforces market concentration. Once stigmatized, a journal is collectively abandoned by authors, with no sign of recovery even several years later. Importantly, this pattern cannot be explained by systemic changes in OA policy, but by the reputational shift itself.

The dependence of China’s OA system on a small cluster of commercial publishers magnified the impact of reputational shifts. The rise of MDPI, and Frontiers throughout the 2010s demonstrates how commercial Gold OA offered a scalable, low-barrier pathway to rapid growth. Yet, the 2020 crisis underscores the structural fragility of this model: reputational challenges, once publicly institutionalized, can rapidly erode legitimacy, irrespective of the technical compliance of these journals with OA standards.

Unlike Hybrid or Green OA models, which remained marginal, for-profit Gold OA provided little resilience. Researchers facing reputational uncertainty did not shift towards domestic, regional journals or Diamond OA outlets; instead, many recalibrated towards legacy publishers with entrenched prestige (Elsevier, Springer-Nature, Wiley, etc.), reinforcing rather than disrupting hierarchical structures.

The dynamics observed highlight the primacy of prestige logics. Even at the height of MDPI’s growth, its attractiveness derived not from epistemic recognition but from instrumental advantages (fast turnaround, WoS and Scopus indexing, affordability). Once these advantages were undermined by reputational stigma, the data shows that authors withdrew and sought safer ground in journals backed by established brands.

This behavioral recalibration reflects deeper structural incentives in the Chinese science system. Promotion criteria, grant evaluations, and institutional rankings continue to valorize journal-based prestige, especially international visibility and citation performance. OA, therefore, remains subordinated to the symbolic economy of reputation.

The Chinese case demonstrates that OA trajectories can be highly vulnerable to reputation traps. Our data supports the hypothesis that these traps occur when the credibility of OA venues rests on fragile perceptions rather than long-term legitimacy. Once reputational shifts take place, they not only discredit individual journals but also trigger systemic reversals in OA adoption, pushing researchers back toward predominating publishers.

Without diversification into Green, Diamond, or community-governed infrastructures, and without decoupling career incentives from journal prestige, OA remains unevenly developed across the publishing landscape. While global statistics indicate that OA is generally on the rise,

this growth is largely concentrated among major commercial publishers, reinforcing their dominance rather than broadening the diversity of publishing models. Consequently, OA in its current form remains limited to specific venues and potentially more precarious, prone to cycles of rapid expansion and collapse. The observed dynamic is therefore not necessarily unique to China but may reflect a broader structural weakness of OA ecosystems dominated by commercial models without corresponding reforms in research assessment.

5. Limitations, Future Directions, and Outlook

This study has focused on NSFC-funded articles as a proxy for Chinese research priorities, and while the NSFC is the largest and most influential funding agency in China, it does not represent the totality of Chinese science. Our reliance on OpenAlex metadata limits the granularity of journal-level quality indicators. Furthermore, the CAS early-warning list has changed over time, and future research could observe data changes for journals on the early-warning list for five consecutive years to study future publishing behavior and whether journals are able to reshape their brands or whether they have “failed” when they once fell into a reputation trap.

Although our results tend to confirm a sharp decline in publications in journals listed on the CAS early-warning list immediately after its release, this effect may have been reinforced by a broader global dynamic against these publishers. The international scientific community has increasingly scrutinized the same publishing groups, which could have acted as a catalyst exacerbating the reputational spiral and accelerating the withdrawal of submissions, even beyond China’s academic system.

We could also expand this analysis by incorporating citation patterns, rejection rates, and author-level strategies across countries with differing academic incentive structures. Additionally, exploring the role of non-monetary incentives (Mazarakis et al., 2025), such as gamification techniques that leverage social interaction, progression, and reward mechanisms, could offer novel ways to promote OA publishing, particularly among smaller, local publishers like those in China. As our empirical study demonstrates evidence for a reputation trap based on the CAS early-warning list, future research can further elaborate on the delineation of the phenomena and their reasons for the cause.

Future work could also explore the influence of institutional agreements and international co-authorship on publisher choice. In particular, it would be informative to examine whether collaborations with researchers from countries enjoying favorable publishing arrangements reinforce the concentration toward top commercial publishers, and how such dynamics interact with OA policies and evaluation pressures. Likewise, research on the perception and usage of Chinese authors consulting the CAS early-warning list within their publishing process and their general preferences and reasons for selection or avoidance of specific journals, publishers, and OA publishing models could further complement the picture apart from the publisher-publication perspective.

Considering, that the CAS early-warning list constitutes a list approach and the past criticism of list like Beall’s List (Beall, 2018; Krawczyk & Kulczycki, 2021; Strielkowski, 2018), it is also important to reconsider the value, boundaries and, limitations of such lists. Especially, as in the case for the CAS early-warning list, the number of listed journals has changed significantly over the last 5 years which might be quite a short period. It is therefore desirable to

further strengthen education on journal selection to not overly rely on lists (Yamada & Teixeira da Silva, 2022).

6. Conclusions

This study traced nearly two decades of OA publishing strategies among NSFC-funded researchers, revealing an unstable trajectory punctuated by cycles of expansion, reputational crisis, and retrenchment. We introduced the hypothesis/phenomena of the *reputation trap* to capture how researchers' OA uptake is tightly coupled to the perceived legitimacy of venues.

Three core conclusions emerge. First, OA adoption in China has been rapid but fragile, heavily dependent on commercial Gold OA infrastructures vulnerable to reputational shocks. Second, these shocks did not lead to diversification into Green or Diamond OA, but instead reinforced the dominance of legacy publishers. Third, reputation acts as a centripetal force that constrains the transformative potential of OA unless policies explicitly target credibility, governance, and evaluation systems.

The Chinese case should not be viewed as exceptional but as illustrative of global tensions in scholarly publishing. Without reforms that decouple academic careers from journal prestige and that build robust, trusted OA infrastructures, OA systems will remain vulnerable to cycles of hype, collapse, and recentralization. Escaping the reputation trap requires coordinated efforts across funders, institutions, and publishers to foster an ecosystem that is open, credible, and sustainable.

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